

“A Study on Diminishing Job Opportunities by Virtue of Artificial Intelligence in BPO Sector- with Specific Reference to Fidelity India Ltd”

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence is used as one of the most effective cost reduction techniques in several fields such as technology, commerce and management, business process outsourcing pertaining to the tasks which is repetitive in nature. The tasks which are repetitive in nature, if done by man power attracts a sizeable amount of compensation to be payable to the hired man-power. In order to avoid this, as a method of cost reduction, artificial intelligence is being used as a substitute for those tasks which are of repetitive nature which at present is being managed by hired manpower. Man power hiring in the present scenario has become a herculean task for the corporates as it absorbs several overheads in the form of recruitment, selection and trying of the man power. Added to it the compensation payable to the man power is proving to be an extravagant cost for the corporates and such huge costs can be considerably minimized by attrition rate at present being managed by the man power, by the artificial intelligence. It is believed that 75% of the total cost being expended on manpower can be saved by installing an artificial intelligence system. Naturally the implication of such mechanism will be instrumental in saving of huge cost which is expended on the manpower at present. This research paper makes a study on how the artificial intelligence system is being implemented in a phased manner in Fidelity India Ltd Bangalore and how this company is adapting itself to artificial intelligence in attrition rate which are of repetitive nature. Only primary data is used in this paper through a direct interview with the HR manager of the company and required information is sought by giving a questioner. This study reveals that in the current financial year about 15% of the jobs are cut in the above mentioned company which will be augmented to 23.33% in the years to come.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, Jobs of repetitive nature, installation of artificial intelligences system, diminishing job opportunities.

Introduction

Fidelity Investments Inc., commonly referred to as Fidelity, is a multinational financial services corporation based in Boston, Massachusetts.

It is the fourth largest asset manager with \$2.4 trillion in assets under management as of December 2017. Fidelity Investments operates a brokerage firm, manages a large family of mutual funds, provides fund distribution and investment advice, retirement services, wealth management, securities execution and clearance, and life insurance and accounting services.

The company was founded as Fidelity Management & Research (FMR) by Edward C. Johnson II in 1946. In 1969, the company formed Fidelity International Limited (FIL) to serve non-U.S. markets. It was spun off in 1980. In 2010, it was rebranded as 'Fidelity Worldwide Investment'. In 1982, the company started offering 401(k) products. In 1984, the company offered computerized stock trading.

In 1997, Robert Pozen was named CEO. In 2010, Fidelity Ventures, its venture capital arm, was shut down, and many of the employees created Volition Capital. In 2011, Fidelity changed the name of its international division from Fidelity International to Fidelity Worldwide Investment and a new logo was introduced. In 2012, the company moved its Boston headquarters to 245 Summer Street.

Fidelity India Ltd was started in the year 2003 in Gurgaon and they have extended their operations and at present there are operating in Bangalore and Chennai and they have their BPO operations in Accounting, Non-banking and Non- insurance Sectors such as Stock market trading, mutual funds, securities, retirement Benefits and other non-banking & non- insurance services

Business Process outsourcing - BPO

BPO sector from a couple of years is providing considerable job opportunities to the youths of our country. Business Process outsourcing, be it in accounting or legal services or banking and insurance will have a regular path in the accomplishment of a particular task & therefore by all means we can say that the procedure involved in BPO jobs are repetitive in nature and there is a scope of introducing the AI in the accomplishment of these jobs which results in diminishing of the job opportunities which at present are accomplished by the human beings. Keeping this concept in mind several BPO companies are equipping themselves towards the installation of AI which results in attrition rate. Fidelity India Ltd. is one such company which has made a strong foot print in the BPO sector and at present is thinking of attrition rate in its BPO sector by installing AI system.

Review of literature

1. Artificial intelligence-based systems applied in industrial marketing: An historical overview, current and future insights
By Francisco J. Martínez-López, Jorge Casillas
2. AI SURVEYING: ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN BUSINESS
By Tomas Eric Nordlander
3. Artificial Bee Colony and Its Application for Image Fusion
By- Prabhat Kumar Sharma, Bhavya V S, Navyashree K M, Sunil K S, Pavithra P
4. IS ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE THE NEXT BIG THING IN HR?
By Sweta Jain

Research Gap

From the above review of literature its evident that no research scholars so far has not undertaken the research in connection with application of AI in BPO sector with specific reference to the Indian scenario.

Statement of the problem

As most of the BPO tasks are of repetitive in nature, several BPO companies are thinking on the lines of installing AI which paves the path for attrition rate in BPO sector which is a debatable and researchable topic as to what extent AI is playing a Pivotal role in attrition rate in BPO sector in the Indian context.

Objectives

1. To understand the relevance of AI in the corporates, dealing with BPO services with specific reference to Fidelity India Ltd.
2. To know how far AI in aiding in abolishing the job opportunities.
3. Whether AI is really instrumental in attrition rate in the above mentioned company.

Limitation of the study

1. The research is confined only to the installation of AI only on BPO sectors.
2. In BPO sector only one company i.e. Fidelity India ltd Bangalore city only is considered.
3. The period of study considered is only for 2 years i.e. 2017-18 & 2018-19 and projection is given only for one year 2019-20.

Research Design

- a. Research type – It is an exploratory research with no comparative analysis by taking only one company into consideration.
- b. Data type – only Primary data is used in the research paper.
- c. Data collection method – Questioner.
- d. Tools used in data analysis: simple bar diagrams.

Data Analysis

- a. Chart showing the quantum of the installation of AI system in accounting services of BPO the company

Year	Percentage of Installation of AI in Accounting Services
2017-18	10
2018-19	13
Projection	
2019-20	20

Interpretation

From the above bar diagram it can be inferred that the percentage of the mechanization of accounting of BPO jobs using AI at Fidelity India ltd. is has increased by 3% and it is projected that it would be augmented by 10% in the year 2019-20.

b. Chart showing the quantum of the installation of AI system in Non-banking services of BPO

Year	Percentage of installation of AI in Non-banking services
2017-18	14
2018-19	18
Projection	
2019-20	25

Interpretation

From the above bar diagram it can be inferred that the AI in Non-banking sector is increased by 4% in the current year and it is expected to grow by 11% in the year 2019-20.

c. Chart showing the quantum of the installation of AI system in Non-insurance sector of BPO

Year	Percentage of installation of AI in Non-insurance Sector
2017-18	10
2018-19	15
Projection	
2019-20	25

Interpretation

From the above bar diagram it can be inferred that the Percentage of Mechanization in Non-insurance sector is increased by 5% in the current year 2018-19 and it is expected to grow by 10% in the year 2019-20.

d. Chart showing the average installation of AI system in all the 3 sector of BPO

Average installation of AI in the current year 2018-19	Average installation of AI in the Projected year 2019-20
15.10	23.33

Interpretation

From the above bar diagram it can be inferred that the installation of AI would be increased by 8% in the year 2019-20 as compared to the current year 2018-19.

e. Chart showing the diminishment of job opportunities in all the 3 sectors of BPO

Year	Percentage diminishment of Job opportunities in BPO
2017-18	5
2018-19	12
Projection	
2019-20	20

Interpretation

From the above bar diagram it can be inferred that the number of people hired by Fidelity India ltd. in its BPO sector is diminished by 7% in the current year 2018-19 i.e. in the year 2017-18, it means to say that the company would not want 5 employees out of 100 hireable employees because of AI & as the percentage of the installation of AI has increased in the current year to 15.1% average, this has resulted in the diminishment of job opportunities up to 12% i.e. in the current year due to mechanization they would not be hiring 12 people out of 100 people whom they are going to hire in the BPO sector. And this percentage would still escalate by 18% in the projected year 2019-20 that means they would not hire 25 people out of 100 people whom they are going to hire the year 2019-20.

Findings and Conclusions

1. It is found that by and large the quantum of installation of AI in the Fidelity India Ltd. is increasing in the above mentioned 3 BPO sectors dealt by Fidelity India Ltd. in the current year 2018-19 and this is still showing increasing trend in the projected year 2019-20.
2. As the percentage of AI system is increasing it is found at the job opportunities in the BPO of this company has slightly diminished in the current year 2018-19 & it is also found that this diminishment would still increase in the projected year 2019-20.
3. It is found that increase in AI system and diminishment of job opportunities in percentages are directly proportional. In other words more the installation is AI system, more would be the chances of attrition rate in BPO in the above mentioned company.
4. It can be inferred that AI is relevant and instrumental in the diminishment of job opportunities.
5. It can be inferred that AI is definitely aiding the company in attrition rate and playing an important role in the cost cutting program of the company.

Further scope of research

The research might be under taken to know the impact of job cuts in BPO sector in the days to come on the un-employability rate in India

References

Magazine Business Standard, Economic times &
www.google.com
www.fidelity.com